

Literature Review Article

Intertextuality in Shahaduz Zaman's "Prithibite Hoyto Brihaspatibar" (It's Maybe Thursday on Earth)

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ABSTRACT

Literature, it turns out, is a collage of other texts. And when a reader immerses in a work of literature, it becomes part of the stuff their experiences are made up from. In the case of writers, this homogenisation of texts is a conscious or unconscious appropriation symptomatically present in their writing procedures. Critical postmodernists would argue that each text already intertwines itself in relation to other palimpsests, a phenomenon known as intertextuality which is, indeed, an old literary technique expressed in the new words. Intertextuality gives layers of meaning to the text by incorporating references to other texts and enhancing the reader's reading experience. Shahaduz Zaman, a contemporary Bangladeshi author, uses intertextuality in his writings by referring to other texts and genres in narratives. Zaman draws an intertextual thread through his short story, "Prithibite Hoyto Brihaspatibar" (It's Maybe Thursday on Earth) to analyse the psychology of the protagonist, place him in a cultural sphere and communicate indirectly with his readers. Referencing historical occurrences, he dates himself within the narrative, attaches significance to the text in its modern context and ensures that his readers do not lose sight of reality outside of fiction. In analysing the multifaceted intertextual aspects of the narrative, this paper is concerned with how they serve to create levels of complexity in storytelling, introduce multiple layers of meaning, and enrich readers' encounters with writing as a form.

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Introduction

Intertextuality occurs when a text references or borrows from another, creating a mutually enriching relationship between them. These references—whether explicit or implicit, conscious or unconscious—affect how meaning is constructed and help position the reader within a broader cultural and literary context. A text gains significance not on its own but as part of this larger network. When a writer incorporates echoes of other works, they add depth and resonance, whether through original insights or borrowed expressions.

Intertextuality functions at several levels: obligatory (when an author intentionally cites another text), optional (when references are used to enrich meaning), and accidental (when readers themselves discover links the author may not have intended). The text being read is the hypertext, and the text being referred to is the hypotext. Devices such as allusion, quotation, calque, translation, pastiche, parody, and others open up multiple possibilities of meaning. When readers can identify such connections—drawn from literature, history, or culture—they recognise the text as part of a wider constellation of references.

Intertextuality is fundamentally a conversation across texts. It plays a vital role in reading because it allows writers to add layers of meaning, create relationships and resonance, engage the reader, and provide enjoyment. Recognizing references to literature, history, or other art forms helps the reader understand how texts connect to one another. These references carry their own contexts and meanings, enriching the surface of the story and placing it within a larger framework—its time period, the author's intentions, and cultural background. Intertextuality also encourages the reader to take an active role in interpretation, where finding connections offers intellectual satisfaction. Thus, it makes reading a more meaningful, richer, and more engaging experience.

Another way to frame intertextuality is through the postmodern belief that nothing is entirely original anymore. All texts are linked to previous texts, drawing heavily from existing contexts, concepts, and media. From this perspective, intertextuality is not only a stylistic device but an inherent condition of literature itself.

It is important to recognise that the practice of creating intertextuality has existed for a significantly longer period than the recently formulated theory of intertextuality. John Milton's 1667 work about the Fall of Man, *Paradise Lost*, is one of the best works of intertextuality ever. *Paradise Lost* takes a text (*The Bible*) and puts it in a new light by looking at it from Satan's point of view. William Shakespeare's famous play *Hamlet* (1603) draws inspiration from several sources, including the revenge tragedy tradition and Norse mythology, adding depth and complexity to the character and plot.

James Joyce's epic novel *Ulysses* (1920) is filled with allusions to classical mythology, history, and literature, creating a complex network of references that enriches the reading experience. Toni Morrison's novel *Beloved* (1987) reinterprets the history of slavery and the American South through various intertextual references, including slave narratives and biblical texts. These works demonstrate how intertextuality has continually enriched literary imagination.

Shahaduz Zaman (1960), a contemporary Bangladeshi writer, is known for his distinctive use of intertextuality. While he writes across translation, essays, novels, and docu-fiction, his strongest literary ground is the short story. The walls of the story often fall apart in his stories, and poetry, essays, and even criticism come in. And here is where other dimensions enter into Zaman's tales. He creates stories with many layers by mixing elements from different genres, which blurs the lines between them and gives readers a sense of 'generic indeterminacy,' which is a widespread trait of postmodern literature. His stories frequently exceed conventional expectations by incorporating reflections, lyrical expressions, and critical asides, which add fresh dimensions to the narrative.

One of Zaman's most intertextually rich works is "Prithibite Hoyto Brihaspatibar" (It's Maybe Thursday on Earth), the fifth story from his collection *Mamlar Shakkhi Moyna Pakhi* (Bird Myna: The Testifier [2019]). He uses dramatic tools to pull readers into the story, making the time and place of the story a stage. He then goes on a journey through intertextuality, using the myth of Kadru and Vinata from the *Mahabharata*, the poem of Binoy Majumdar, and the music of Frank Sinatra as inspiration. This literary collage, which is a quintessential feature of Zaman's storytelling, creates a vibrant and layered narrative experience.

Literature Review

The term 'intertextuality' was developed in the 1960s by Bulgarian-born French philosopher and literary critic Julia Kristeva. She coined this term in her writing on Bakhtin's Dialogism and Carnival. Derived from the Latin word 'intertexto', which describes the process of interweaving, Kristeva argues that all texts are engaged in a never-ending 'dialogue' with other texts. In her view, the text can only be fully understood through an integration of its interconnected and interdependent parts.

Russian philosopher and literary critic Mikhail Bakhtin has significantly contributed to the concept of dialogism or polyphony in literature. Although he did not employ the term 'intertextuality' explicitly, his concepts have also nourished it. In his essay "Discourse in the Novel" (from the book *The Dialogic Imagination: Four Essays* [1981]), he suggests that every act of utterance is a social as well as an aesthetic transaction, and meaning occurs only through the interaction of multiple voices and viewpoints.

Mikhail Bakhtin's insistence on primacy and dialogue between voices, perspectives, and genres in language led his 'dialogic' notions of life to provide prescripts for social research. His notions of dialogue laid a foundation for later theorists like Kristeva and Roland Barthes. Bakhtin's theoretical model, in which texts are engaged in a dynamic conversation that invokes and transforms other works, suggested the wide-ranging explorations of intertextuality by subsequent critics.

Kristeva sees a kinship between Bakhtin's dialogism and her own notion of intertextuality. In the essay "Word, Dialogue and Novel" (from the collection *Desire in Language: A Semiotic Approach to Literature and Art* [1980]), she states that dialogue is an inherent trait of all texts. Her observation reinforces the idea that meaning is dialogic and

historically situated. Kristeva emphasises the contribution of intertextuality to social meaning. She suggests that texts are never separate from their social or historical context. Through an examination of intertextual references in a given text, however, it is possible for a reader to learn more about the ideologies and power structures that support the text.

Although it is easier to associate the origin of intertextuality as a (critical) concept with Mikhail Bakhtin and Julia Kristeva, the French essayist and literary critic Roland Barthes played an important role in setting its direction. Barthes (1977) says it best: “The text is a tissue of quotations drawn from the innumerable centres of culture” (p. 146). This reinforces the notion that texts are not self-contained entities, but rather tapestries of features taken from elsewhere. His view reveals the mutual relations and dependence among texts situated in a particular socio-cultural matrix.

In his famous essay, “The Death of the Author,” Barthes contests the idea that authorial intention determines meaning. Once a text enters public culture, meaning becomes open—constructed through intertextual links and the reader’s own experiences. This paradigm, which centres text and reader over author, profoundly influenced later studies of intertextuality.

In his essay “From Work to Text” (published in *Image, Music, Text* [1977]), Barthes imagines the text as a fluid arena within which meaning is not static and determinate but generated through an interplay of elements; it is negotiated. He then underscores playful and inventive facets of intertextuality, drawing out how texts may question, parody, or recast already existing meanings. Barthes then describes metatextuality as the manner in which a text provides commentary on itself and its own composition. He claims that texts frequently provide indices of and allusions to their own intertextuality, soliciting readers to collaborate in the production of meaning.

Though the word ‘intertextuality’ as such is of very recent origin in literary studies, the ancient practice of textual borrowing (‘borrowing from other texts’) appears to be at least as old as texts themselves. This is evidenced in a wide range of examples from the canon of world literature, from Milton to Morrison. The tradition itself historically extends to Bengali literature, where cross-referencing and dialogue between multiple literary texts gleam through on the pages.

Michael Madhusudan Dutt’s epic poem *Meghnad Badh Kavya* (1861) is a retooling of Valmiki’s *Ramayana* and Homer’s *The Iliad* that highlights the death of Meghnada when he and Rama come into battle one last time. The text which has been revisited is *Meghnad Badh Kavya*, weaving into its intertextuality ideas about love, war, and duty as embodied in the earlier works, but also providing a different perspective on the heroes and their goodness or otherwise. Rabindranath Tagore’s *Gitanjali* (1910), a collection of poems, frequently quotes from sacred texts including the *Upanishads* and the *Bhagavad Gita*. He has been influenced by the folk and Baul music; he uses their forms and themes in his poems. This intertextual discourse enhances the interpretation of Tagore’s verses and enables readers to place them within larger cultural and religious traditions.

Kazi Nazrul Islam's "Bidrohi" (1922), the rebel poem, is full of references to figures and events, including the Sepoy Mutiny of 1857 and the Bengal Renaissance. These intertextual references ground the poem in history as well as resonate with the revolutionary fervour of earlier generations. Jibanananda Das's celebrated poem "Banalata Sen" (1935) mixes up materials from Greek mythology, European literature, and old-fashioned Bengali folklore. Das weaves a sophisticated, multi-faceted narrative that penetrates the realms of desire, memory, and existential persistence by using varying intertextual references, which enliven his poetry.

In the literary heritage, Shahaduz Zaman appears as a remarkable icon in contemporary Bengali literature. His writing has been prolific: numerous collections of short stories, novels, travel books, essays, not to mention film scripts. His writing is widely appreciated for his bitter-sweet observation of society, his language and word skills, and the formal experimentation.

Incidentally, Zaman seamlessly incorporates fiction, non-fiction, and even lines of poetry into his work. It results in an interesting intertextuality, where genre and aesthetics have an impact upon and interact with each other. He's fond of making references to key events, persons, and literature. It is for this reason that readers could associate his works and, in turn, themselves with more general cultural/literary/social practices.

For instance, in "Onno Ek Galpoker Golpo Niye Golpo" (A Story About Another Storyteller's Story [2014]), he narrates the tale of an aspiring writer under the penumbra of a story by Jibanananda Das, while simultaneously offering an analysis of Jibanananda's hypotext. In "Anna Karenina Janaika Pathika" (A Reader of Anna Karenina [1999]), he juxtaposes the plot of Leo Tolstoy's *Anna Karenina* (1878) with the fragile dynamics of a young Bangladeshi couple, presenting alongside it a comparative reading of Russian and Bangladeshi socio-political contexts. "Ogalpo" (The Non-Story [1996]) adopts a deliberately anti-narrative form to articulate a distinctive interpretation of Bangladesh's liberation and its subsequent historical evolution.

Zaman's writing tends to fold back on itself, foregrounding its own construction. It is this metafictional impulse that encourages readers to consider textuality, narrative authority, and the creation of meanings. By reappropriating older stories and myths—sometimes reanimating them, sometimes interrogating them—he extends the creative and critical reach of intertextuality. His intentional use of intertextual references functions as a mode of cultural critique that invites readers into an interpretive space where social and ethical questions are explored with nuance and intellectual rigour.

Zaman's writing has a habit of turning back on itself and examining its own makeup. This metafictional stance encourages the reader to think about textuality and authorial function. He reframes old stories and myths, giving new meaning to and, in many cases, disputing tradition. This transformation process enhances the dynamic and creative potential of intertextuality. Zaman critiques social and cultural injustices by intertextual referencing in a way that weaves the work invitingly into our interpretation to provoke critical thinking and reflection, serving readers.

Intertextually exploiting the stories of Shahaduz Zaman uncouples a deep-rooted appreciation for his work and enriches the reading experience. Recognising echoes of literature, history, mythology, and contemporary realities opens up multiple layers of meaning. Intertextuality enables him to explore universal themes—love, loss, selfhood, and the search for meaning—across cultures and time. Placed within a larger context of literature, the reader sees how he responds to and revises earlier writing, with his new work joining the chorus that is literature. It also situates his writing within a broader literary continuum, showing how his texts respond to earlier works and contribute to ongoing dialogues.

Moreover, as intertextuality allows for the development of new readings and reading perspectives, it enriches the interactive nature of a reading experience. The reader gets a closer sense of his cultural roots and of the social history surrounding his stories by knowing where he drew from. This method can also contribute to readers' enjoyment of and interest in the works alluded to, enticing them toward further exploration, enhancing their literary knowledge and understanding, and enabling them to appreciate more fully the plethora of literature.

Intertextual Dialogues

The story is a bit about romance and a lot about corporate politics and deception. Masood, the protagonist of the story, works in the communication department of a corporate company. Sitting at a tea stall on a rainy day one afternoon, he shares with his boss, Kaiser Haque, an idea for marketing. It is on Thursday. On Sunday, after the weekend, Masood goes to the office and finds Haque sharing the concept in a meeting with the senior management as his own. Masood is shocked by this.

Back in his apartment, Masood phones his girlfriend, Ruma. He tells her to open a page in the paper. A shy monkey¹ has been rescued at Netrokona. Masood gets Ruma to read the news. She can't quite grasp what Masood has in mind.

The issue, according to Masood, is that it's not actually a monkey. It is one of the species in the Lemur group, which belongs to the primates. It has been thrown into the monkey's identity erroneously. It resembles a monkey but is no monkey at all. It's helpless, and it glances around with vulnerable eyes. It has somehow ended up here, where it isn't meant to be. He adds that humans, too, can do it. A man who may be among men, but is not a man, actually. He might be something else. He's actually stuck in human form. He does not know how to deal with this identity. He looks around with shame...

This conversation is quintessential Kaiser Haque. In this human figure, albeit inhumanly so, the paradox of humanity's identity reveals itself as a plot twist toward the story's conclusion. The analogy also becomes central to the story's unfolding tension. The confused, misidentified creature becomes a metaphor for Masood's own alienation—a thematic

¹ A primate, specifically the Bengal slow loris, locally known as Lajjabati Banor (shy monkey).

movement Zaman has explored in other works such as “Mohashunye Cycle” (A Bicycle in Outer Space [2012]), “Murakamir Biral” (The Cat of Murakami [2014]), and “Tukro Roder Moto Kham” (An Envelope Like a Beam of Sunlight [2019]). In these stories, too, characters inhabit ambiguous identities, caught between social expectations and inner truth. This intertextual continuity strengthens the argument that Zaman uses intertextual metaphors to deepen the emotional and philosophical layers of his narratives.

Shahaduz Zaman employs dramatic descriptions to slide into the story. The story of the environment sets both the time and place in which the story is set into a stage. The world of the story’s setting, with everything that goes on in it, stands as a playhouse set open before the reader. The characters are listed as actors and actresses on the stage. The narrator asserts: Light fades away from all sides like a stage. Clouds hem in, like a set for the most climactic scene of a play. A thunderstorm breaks out... Masood walks. He is feeling helpless (Zaman, 2019, p. 42).

The writer drenches the setting of this story with a dramatic atmosphere where genres such as play and narrative are melded within the story. This integration of intertextuality presents itself as a postmodernist stylistic feature, most clearly in controlled generic indeterminacy² within the descriptive passages.

The storyteller describes, “On stage, all the actors and actresses stare at the incessant rain and think quietly” (Zaman, 2019, p. 42). Through comparisons of characters in the story and the actors on stage, it puts forth the notion of Simulacra³ into context and presents it in a relevant manner. The French philosopher Jean Baudrillard (1994) states, “Simulation is no longer that of a territory, a referential being, or a substance. It is the generation by models of a real without origin or reality: a hyperreal” (p. 1). In this story, the word is substituted for reality. It also obliterates the separation between reality and imaging, rendering the character’s reality hyperreal in terms of their narrative world.

Also, an unforgettable quote by Shakespeare (2001/1599) may peep into the mind of the reader while reading this description— “All the world’s a stage, and all the men and women merely players” (*As You Like It*, Act II, Scene 7).

The author, thus, creates an intertextual space inside the description by mixing genres and working with different concepts of the short story form.

In the initial scene, when the thunder commences, Masood’s mobile rings. His girlfriend, Ruma, is on the other end of the line: “Go stand under a shed” (Zaman, 2019, p. 42). And as he processes all of this, a Frank Sinatra song plays in Masood’s mind:

Fly Me to the Moon.
Let me play among the stars.
And let me see what spring is like
On Jupiter and Mars...
In other words, I love you (Howard, 1954)

² A term used to describe the blurring of genre boundaries, often associated with postmodern literature.

³ A concept from postmodern philosophy, referring to a representation or imitation that has replaced the original, challenging notions of reality.

He ponders over what Ruma said, “Go stand under a shed.” What is she trying to say? Masood interprets, “Go stand under a shed... In other words, I love you.” The author inserts an underlying meaning into the dialogue “Go stand under a shed” with the reference to Sinatra’s song, which simultaneously introduces the cultural sphere of the protagonist (and the author) and exemplifies the indirect manner in which people in this region typically express their emotions. In his book *Intertextuality*, Irish academic Graham Allen (2000) states, “Intertextuality involves the shaping of texts’ meanings by other texts” (p. 5). Here, the author deliberately shapes the meaning of his character’s dialogue with another text—the jazz song “In Other Words,” generating a deeper emotional resonance and showcasing his distinctive use of cultural references.

The author derives the title of the story “Prithibite Hoyto Brihaspatibar” from the poem “Aaj Brihaspatibar” (Today is Thursday) by Binoy Majumdar (1934–2006), a Bengali poet. This can be considered the author’s homage to his predecessor poet. Moreover, the poem serves as an overview of the mental state of the story’s protagonist, Masood. While sharing the marketing idea at the tea stall, Masood recites Majumdar’s poetry to Kaiser Haque.:

আজ বৃহস্পতিবার: পৃথিবীতে হয়তো বৃহস্পতিবার নয়
মাঠে মাঠে ছাগল ঘাস খাচ্ছে, তাদের পিঠে লাগছে
মহাজগতের রোদ। আমারও ঘুমানোর সময়
হয়ে এলো। কিন্তু একদা ভুট্টা চন্দ্রসিক্ত হয়েছিলো
এই স্মৃতি মনে করে আমি ঘুমাতে পারি না
বসে বসে ম্যাচ বাক্সের কাঠি গুনি। (Majumdar, 2017)

A rough translation⁴ of the poem reads: “Today is Thursday: Maybe it isn’t Thursday on Earth. Goats are cropping in the field and the sun of the cosmos on their backs. I have to sleep too. But still I can’t sleep, thinking some more of how the memory was kind to the moon-soaked corn. I sit and number the matchbox sticks.”

Haque still seems perplexed by the poem. Masood reassures him that he doesn’t really need to understand. Instead, he recommends imagining a man sitting by himself, counting matchsticks. Masood elaborates on the scenario: The man tries to take a nap at noon, but he glances that goat are grazing under the sunlight in the field outside his window. All the dumb triviality of sunshine is worm-holed into cosmic importance from the man’s point of view. It evokes another cosmic event—moonlight on a cornfield on a peaceful night. Haunted by this recollection, the man cannot sleep, and thus, whiles away the hours counting matchsticks.

Masood extracts the singular from what might be a run-of-the-mill poem, one that invokes cosmic matters while alluding to solitude, and amid the peaceful setting of a moonlit cornfield. It becomes apparent that Masood has a deep understanding of life and the shared world we inhabit. The poem also gestures toward Masood’s social standing and state of mind,

⁴ All translations from Bengali source texts into English are the work of the author of this paper.

revealing how he is cognizant of the loneliness expressed in the lines. It is an indication of the emotional fragility and loneliness of Masood. In the poem, too, counting matchsticks works as a metaphorical reflection of Masood's own gesture to share ideas with Haque—an intimate gesture exposed to potential betrayal.

Allen (2000) recognises this way of storytelling by affirming, “Meaning becomes something which exists between a text and all the other texts to which it refers and relates, moving out from the independent text into a network of textual relations” (p. 1). In the story, meaning indeed emerges in the space between Majumdar's poem, Sinatra's jazz track, Shakespeare's dramatic metaphor, Baudrillard's theory, and Zaman's narrative style. This intertwined textual tapestry enhances the emotional and philosophical depth of Masood's character, and requires, as well, a broader literary method on Zaman's part.

Story within a Story

At one point in the story, the author discloses Masood's weekend pastime of watching American crime drama series *Breaking Bad* (2008–13). With mentions to Frank Sinatra, Binoy Majumder, and the likes of telly shows, the author takes control of his protagonist, Masood's psyche. At the same time, there would be a second parallel reading where the author would indirectly be communicating to the reader by inserting meta-references to other art media in his narrative. Throughout the story, the author reveals some of Masood's tastes and preferences in a relaxed yet somehow subversive manner. With unapologetic frequency, Shahaduz Zaman states in the interviews that he has not set out to write literature that reflects the taste of readers; instead, he prefers to create readers' taste as well.

And it's through these intertextual inserts—from global pop culture to Bengali poetry—that he carries out not just an aesthetic agenda but also, in a way, covertly. Like Masood, these devices both humanise him and locate Zaman in a line of writers who use intertextuality to both expand and destabilise the reader's interpretive instincts. This strategy closely reflects his treatment in other works, such as “Onno Ek Galpokarer Golpo Niye Golpo” (A Story About Another Storyteller's Story [2014]), “Bookshelve Bagh” (Tiger on the Bookshelf [2012]), and “Anna Kareninar Janaika Pathika” (A Reader of Anna Karenina [1999]), where references to real writers, paintings, and political history similarly function as quiet cultural interventions.

Deceived Masood is called by Ruma once he goes under a shed. She asks if he is sheltered and adds, “Don't come out until it stops raining. Instead, wait.” Masood decides to wait. And while he waits during this interval, he is reminded of a story from the *Mahabharata* about waiting: Kadru and Vinata, two lovely daughters of Daksha Prajapati. One day, their husband, Kashyapa, said, ‘I will grant you boons, what boons do you wish?’ Kadru replied, ‘Let me have a thousand powerful Nagas.’ Kashyapa gave her that boon. Then Vinata said, ‘Give me two sons who will excel those of Kadru in strength and vigour.’ Kashyapa had granted her that boon too. Kadru gave birth to a thousand eggs. A few days later, Vinata bore two more of these.

Then days passed, years passed. Thus, it came to pass, after the lapse of five centuries, that one day all of Kadru's thousand eggs cracked open and a thousand Nagas were born. Except that nothing hatched from the eggs of Vinata. Then Vinata became impatient. And then she cracked one of her two eggs to check out what was inside. As the egg broke, Vinata saw that her son had a head and upper half of a body, but was devoid below. Her incomplete son got very annoyed with her breaking the egg out of impatience. He cursed his mother from within the egg, in rage. He said, 'You were insatiable, and so my body was left incomplete. For this, you will have to become a servant of your sister Kadru for five hundred years.' Vinata was saddened by her son's curse. The son said, 'Then you may be free from this curse, if you do not crack the other egg too soon. And one day, the brother born from that egg will take your chains off. Wherefore, wait till the egg hatches itself' (Adi Parva, Chapters 15-16; Vyasa, 1961).

The storyteller composes, "Masood will wait. He's willing to bide his time, and wait to find out who and where will hatch an egg and release him from bondage" (Zaman, 2019, p. 49). He compares the corporate servitude of Masood with that of a mythical Vinata. Just as Vinata doesn't know when her son (who would free her from slavery) will be born, Masood too does not know when and how he will rid himself of his shackles of bondage and helplessness in this deceitful city. Because this puts Masood's ordinary helplessness together with the epic helplessness of the mythological figure, the author brings to his narrative a tremendous human depth and subtlety that makes something profound of its meaning. This action broadens Masood's plight beyond the personal, towards a more collective situation of being bound within systems—corporate, social, or existential.

In the famous novel, *The Name of the Rose*, Umberto Eco (1983) states, "Books always speak of other books, and every story tells a story that has already been told" (p. xxiv). In this instance, the ongoing story speaks of a mythological story, reaffirming Eco's observation. By making Masood's moment of waiting echo through millennia-old myth, Zaman fuses past and present—and engineers a level of intertextuality that weaves together mythology, modern life, and human frailty.

What makes Zaman's intertextual technique particularly unique is how he harnesses references not into ornamental allusions, but as psychological prompts towards the character's internal climate. However, aside from a few other modern Bangla writers of fiction—Hasan Azizul Huq, Syed Manzoorul Islam, or Imtiaz Shamim—who also work with history, myth, and cultural memory in their narratives, they tend to do so more as thematic or philosophical intertext than as elements entwined with narrative itself. Zaman, however, often makes use of these references to modulate consciousness itself.

Tissues of the Time

After the rain ceases, Masood goes back to the flat and sits in front of his laptop, trying to read the news. A news alert catches his eye: Someone drove a car into pedestrians on London's Westminster Bridge. Several people died. A girl throws herself from the bridge into the River Thames. The assailant was shot dead by police. That attack was classified as a terrorist attack

by the police. However, the police are enquiring into whether the terrorist is a loner, a ‘lone wolf’.⁵

The news carries quite an absurd description. The description of haphazard deaths seems to paint a picture of Masood's internal bleeding. Meanwhile, the author stamps a sense of time in the narration by evoking the infamous Westminster Attack⁶ which took place on March 22, 2017. This inclusion provides the reader with a sense of the story's timeline. The author also includes that the police are also looking at whether the terrorist is a ‘lone wolf’. Masood, seeing the lonely man in “Aaj Brihaspatibar,” reflects a profound parallel to some extent with the lone wolf terrorist who struck on Wednesday in Westminster. If a reader becomes intrigued and even turns to the news, s/he will find out that the name of the attacker in Westminster is Khalid Masood. The story's protagonist, Masood, is named after him.

Yet the parallel immediately splits. Khalid Masood was a 52-year-old man, whereas the fictional Masood is young, waiting, wandering, almost contemplative. The massacre committed by the old lone wolf in 82 seconds⁷ of rampage, Masood is not going to do that; he will not, or at least do something similar. The narrator has already made it clear that Masood prefers anticipation. He is willing to wait, if he has to wait as long as Vinata did, in order to grasp the vagaries of life.

It is by such precise juxtapositioning and distancing of real and fictional identities that Zaman shows himself to be a capable manipulator of intertextual references for multilayered narrative focalization. While its conventional counterpart, like the latter productions, could have effectively reproduced historical events directly through intertextuality, Zaman infuses social statements with a level of ethical and emotional depth that would not be possible in the former form of realism.

In another part of his news reading, Masood is sucked in by a headline: A shy monkey, caught in Durgapur Netrokona by Amirul Islam, now at home with him. His brother, Tajul Islam, shared a photo on Facebook. The Forest Department's Wildlife Crime Unit was called in, and the Shy Monkey Research and Conservation Project responded. Masood phones Ruma, asking, “Can you see his eyes? How helpless! How scared he is!” (Zaman, 2019, p. 51).

Ruma doesn't get it. She wonders why he is suddenly obsessing over a monkey. Masood elaborates: That is my problem. It's the part about being called a monkey that's my problem. It's not actually a monkey. It is a Primate animal belonging to the Lemur group. Folks have been nerd sniping it into the monkey group. They also named it Lajjabati (Shy)! The poor creature belongs elsewhere. It's in there by accident and then accidentally flung into the monkey's identity. This is unfair. Look at his two eyes. How vulnerable! It doesn't want to be here.

⁵ Typically used to describe an individual who acts alone in a terrorist or criminal context.

⁶ A terrorist attack occurred on Westminster Bridge in London on March 22, 2017.

⁷ According to *A Report on The Use of Terrorism Legislation* by Max Hill QC, the duration of the Westminster Attack is approximately 82 seconds.

Ruma senses that something is wrong with Masood. He could have zoned into something. Someone might have cheated him. She asks him. Masood answers: What happened to this animal could happen to anyone. A man may be inside a human, look like a human, but not be the same as them. Maybe something else. Perhaps he stumbled into the human dimension by mistake. And then he is stuck being a man. He doesn't want that identity. He is actually very ashamed. He is gazing around in great terror and humiliation.

Masood's reflections on the displaced 'shy monkey' take on an added significance when viewed alongside his encounter with Kaiser Haque. Mostly, this conversation is in reference to his boss, Mr. Haque. Masood finds Haque not human enough. Such deception, humans are perpetrating, cannot logically be a human attribute. He is not even conflicted or torn on this point. At one moment in the tale, the teller says, "A strong wind blows. As if someone whispers in the wind that the skill of cheating is the Mantra (armour) of survival in this city" (Zaman, 2019, p. 43). It is not normal that the abnormal can now be a regular life affair in the form of deceit. This is the same as in the case of the primate being caught, so it should not be based on that shy monkey's identity. The idea that the shy monkey in the tale is part of this normalcy, however, is exploded by the author.

Beneath this indication lies Masood's own unspoken alienation. Like the primate misidentified and thrust into an unfamiliar order, Masood too finds himself trapped within an identity he did not choose—corporate functionary, obedient subordinate, reluctant participant in a morally eroded city. The shy monkey's terror and humiliation mirror Masood's internal dislocation, his sense of being misaligned with the social world he inhabits.

Interestingly enough, the shy monkey rescue really did happen. There is a keen little twist in this narrative where the author brings something real written about an event into the story. This incident was covered by the *Prothom Alo* newspaper on 29 March, 2017.

Thus, the intertextual echo between the actual event and Masood's state of mind is a metaphorical pivot; the fluttering away of the monkey becomes a muted allegory for Masood's sense of his own existential displacement, while at once embodying corporate predatory logic and its unseen identity crisis.

Drawing on multiple intertextual layers—news, poetry, song, and myth—Zaman enacts Barthes's (1977) claim that "any text is a new tissue of past citations" (p. 39) and Kristeva's (1980) notion of the text as "a mosaic of quotations" (p. 66). Unlike other writers of his time who use preceding texts as mere decoration, Zaman turns intertextuality into a formal and ethical strategy. And by comparing Masood's waiting with Vinata's legendary patience or the monkey's vulnerability to human social alienation and displacement, he enriches both narrative resonance and thematic nuance. The contrast between the global catastrophe (Westminster) and local micro-event (monkey rescue) typifies postmodern oscillation between major and minor, constructing a hyperreal narrative in which reality and fiction constantly interact.

In this way, Zaman employs both narrative novelty and commentary. His strategy of using one text to interpret the other is not decorative but forms our reading, ethics, and intellect. Masood's stories, through historical plots, mythical figures, and ways of life, intercultural references, weave a path for readers to travel meaningfully through different layers, where human vulnerability and bailout emerge alongside patience and ethical consciousness. In doing

so, Zaman pushes the bounds of intertextuality beyond mere literary homage to position his work in a larger conversation about new narrative practices and their relationship to social conditions.

Poetic Palimpsest

The story takes a romantic turn at this point, with Ruma saying, “Masood, hang up. I am coming to you.” The author continues, “Ruma puts down the phone and goes out to Masood’s. Like a brightly yellow-footed starling, she will now sit on Masood’s heavy chest” (Zaman, 2019, p. 51). Zaman employs the metaphor of a starling bird with bright yellow feet to depict Ruma’s approach to Masood. At the sight of this metaphor, any reader familiar with it will be bristling with recollections of Jibanananda Das (1899–1954), one of the most significant Bengali poets. ‘Starling’s yellow feet’ is one of Jibanananda’s recurrent signature images in various poems. For instance, Jibanananda (2023) writes in the poem

“Jiban Othoba Mrityu” (Life or Death),

“আমি এ ঘাসের বুকে শুয়ে থাকি— শালিখ নিয়েছে নিঙড়ায়ে / নরম হলুদ পায়ে এই ঘাস...”

(I rest on the chest of this grass— / the starling has caressed it dry / with its tender yellow feet... [9–10]).

In the poem “Tomra Jekhane Sadh” (Wherever You Wish),

“দেখিব খয়েরি ডানা শালিখের সন্ধ্যায় হিম হয়ে আসে / ধবল রোমের নিচে তাহার হলুদ ঠ্যাং ঘাসে অন্ধকারে”
(At dusk, I’ll see the brown-winged starling freeze, / its yellow feet dim beneath pale feathers in the darkened grass [3–4]).

And in the poem “He Hridoy” (O Heart):

হলুদ দু-ঠ্যাং তুলে নেচে রোগা শালিখের মতো যেন কথা

বলে চলে তবুও জীবন:

বয়স তোমার কত? চল্লিশ বছর হল?

প্রণয়ের পালা ঢের এল গেল—

হল না মিলন? (11–15)

A basic translation of the lines might convey:

“Lifting its yellow legs, life dances on— like a lean starling still speaking: How old are you now? Forty years? So many seasons of love have come and gone— was there no union?”

The storyteller utilises this metaphor twice in the narrative, thus making it a deliberate intertextual collage. Unfortunately, though, borrowing the words, metaphors, or imagery of others is frowned upon in the Bengali literary sphere. It should be understood that the use of such references does not imply that the author is limited to or even lacks originality for such terms. Instead, deftly weaving in others’ words is a powerful statement of craft and the writer’s ability to integrate different strands of the story. In his influential essay “Discourse in the Novel,” Mikhail Bakhtin (1981) describes, “The word in language is half someone else’s. It becomes one’s ‘own’ only when the speaker populates it with his own intentions, his own accent, when he appropriates the word” (p. 294).

Borrowed words, metaphors, and images are capable of building a literary bridge between texts and creating complexity in the reader's experience when used echoingly. The author inserts the word 'bright' in between Jibanananda's image of 'starling's yellow feet' (Zaman writes, 'brightly yellow-footed starling'). Hence, the metaphor shines like a diamond in relation to the story. It must be stressed, however, that "Every utterance must be regarded as primarily a response to preceding utterances of the given sphere" (Bakhtin, 1986, p. 91).

Zaman wraps up his story on this poetic note that is so characteristic of his interweaving of the literary. By weaving elements from classical Bengali poetry into contemporary storytelling, he constructs a layered literary collage, exemplifying how intertextuality amplifies both narrative depth and stylistic distinctiveness.

Conclusion

Shahaduz Zaman blends intertextual fragments in "Prithibite Hoyto Brihaspatibar" to produce a story that resists genre. The story is told through a mixture of classical Bengali poetry and Indian mythology, combined with Western music, literature, and real-world events, which provides readers with a rich reading experience.

Introducing the protagonist's state of mind, the author uses Frank Sinatra's song and Binoy Majumder's poem to create a smooth characterisation. By embedding these intertextual features in the story, implicit explorations of the art forms that are evoked are opened and lightly engaged by entering into some delicate views on Masood's state of mind. The author marvellously stimulates the reader's interest by means of allusions to a wide range of literary material.

The use of intertextual references, it will be argued, contributes to the multilayering of the narrative so that implicit meanings are written into what appear as ordinary dialogues. This arouses the curiosity of the reader, then leads to experiencing deeper meanings for diverse events in the story. Parallel to the internal discomforts of the protagonist, and using a mythical event as an extension, it demonstrates the depth and universality of the feelings and emotions of being.

Intriguingly, the progressing timeline, as well as this technique of placing historical events side by side with fictional ones, manages to keep it temporally topical and lines it up relatively neatly in the path of history. This skilful play with intertext helps to make the reader's reception a rich, multi-dimensional traverse of the text.

The paper has thus been able to investigate and discuss intertextuality in "Prithibite Hoyto Brihaspatibar", and the contributory factor it makes in enhancing the narrative complexity, introducing multiplicity of meaning, and adding to the reader's pleasure of overall reading. And it attracts the reader's attention to intertextual reading and analysis of texts.

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